

Patient Data Protection in Healthcare: A Comprehensive Assessment of Cybersecurity Best Practices among System End-Users. A Case of Peramiho Mission Hospital

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Article History:

Received: 26.05.2025 Revised: 10.06.2025 Accepted: 12.06.2025 Published: 14.06.2025

ABSTRACT:

The objective of the study was to examine the shortcomings of cybersecurity practices by healthcare system end-users in patients' data protection. The study employed mixed methods using the cross-sectional design. The study was conducted at Peramiho Mission Hospital located in Ruvuma, the southern Region of Tanzania. The area was suitable as there were incidences related to data breach associated with system end-users. Primary data were collected using self-administered questionnaires from 161 system end-users who were randomly selected from different departments. Also, 11 heads of departments were interviewed. Secondary data were collected using the documentary guide including data on incidences of data breach and policy guidelines of the organization regarding patient data protection. Quantitative data were analysed using the SPSS package version 26 especially for data entry, and data analysis for generating descriptive statistics. Additionally, R package version 4.3.4 was used to graphically visualize data and produce correlation analysis results. On the other hand, qualitative data were analysed using the thematic analysis methods. The study found that there was increasing trend of incidences involving unintended use of patient data, documentation forgery of patient data, and unauthorized disclosure of patient data. The study found that there was very strong positive significant relationship between cybersecurity best practices including the system end-user conception of the significance of data protection [$r_s = 0.85$, $p\text{-value} < 0.001$], the system end-user training on data protection [$r_s = 0.90$, $p\text{-value} < 0.001$], and the system end-user compliance monitoring [$r_s = 0.89$, $p\text{-value} < 0.001$]. Thus, the moderate level of data protection was a result of the shortcomings in cybersecurity best practices. The study found three major shortcomings of cybersecurity practices including the limited end-user conception of the significance of data protection, inadequacy of end-users training on data protection, and the lack of end-user compliance monitoring.

Keywords: Patient Data, Data Protection, Cybersecurity Practices, system end-user.

Suggested Citation: E.M. Kwesigabo, L.I. Komba, "Patient Data Protection in Healthcare: A Comprehensive Assessment of Cybersecurity Best Practices among System End-Users. A Case of Peramiho Mission Hospital," *Eur. J. Appl. Sc. Eng. Technol.*, vol. 3(3), pp. 360-371, May-Jun 2025. DOI: 10.59324/ejaset.2025.3(3).25

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INTRODUCTION

Data protection is emerging as a serious concern in the healthcare sectors worldwide. Studies have found that a key difference between the healthcare sectors and other industries when it comes to data breaches is that the majority of them originate from within the healthcare system, rather than from outside sources [1]. Meanwhile, more than half of the data breaches in the healthcare industries, 53%, were caused by the negligence of employees who mishandled their login details or the confidential information of patients, making the healthcare system vulnerable to cyberattacks [2]. As a result, studies suggest that the trend of data breaches is still increasingly high in healthcare sectors than in other sectors across countries. In the USA for example, data breaches in the healthcare sector increased from 61.5% in 2005 to 76.6% in 2019 compared to other sectors [2].

The problem is increasing on a large scale in Africa given the accelerating Information and Communication Technology (ICT) adoption in healthcare services [3]. In the context of Africa, the problem of insecurity around patient data is commonly involving unauthorized access to sensitive patient information. Patient data breaches were estimated at 300 million in the year 2023 which is more than double the breaches in year 2022 [4]. Data breach is a cybersecurity threats plaguing healthcare sector in Africa as 725 breaches affected at least 500 patients' records [4]. Nevertheless, patient data breach is associated with huge costs with some breaches exceeding \$10 million [5].

Extensive patient data breaches in Africa are associated with inadequate implementation of cybersecurity best practices [6]. It was also reported that there are cybersecurity awareness gaps among employees in healthcare sector who happen to constitute majority of healthcare system end-users [6]. For example, in Uganda, end-user negligence is associated with data security breach as a result of non-compliance to the best practices especially among junior medical students compared to medical staff [7]. Such negligence in adhering to best practices lead to unauthorized access to sensitive patient information. Other studies found that there is insufficient security and privacy measures, and weak eHealth governance in Uganda [7,8]. On the other hand, in Nigeria, privacy and security vulnerabilities regarding patient data are linked to gaps in information sharing [9]. Data breaches occur through information sharing between system end-users including healthcare professionals and providers in healthcare facilities and during cross-border data transfer at large [9].

Meanwhile, in Tanzania, as healthcare facilities both public and private increasingly streamline Electronic Healthcare Management Information System (EHMIS), understanding the current state of cybersecurity practices by system end-users in the healthcare sector is of merit [10]. Tanzania, like many other nations, faces ongoing concerns of cyberthreats in which case the healthcare sector is not an exception [11]. Most organizations including those involved in healthcare services delivery struggle to keep pace with the evolving threat spectrum including threats emerging from system end-users in particular, leading to potential vulnerabilities in their systems [12]. ICT literacy is low which could be associated with failures in cybersecurity best practices among system end-users [13]. This signifies that there is still room for improvement through studying robust practices in the healthcare sector [11].

Meanwhile, there is an increasing trend of ICT adoption in healthcare services coupled with healthcare facilities having to streamline digital information systems in handling patient data. Despite efforts to embed cybersecurity within emerging cyberspace in healthcare, still there is evidence of a scarcity of patient data protection [2]. Studies show that there is a heightened risk of patient data breach resulting from system end-user's negligence or collaboration leading to loss, theft, or disclosure of sensitive healthcare data [14,15]. Similar examples are emerging in Tanzania healthcare facilities [16]. The scope of data protection failures arising from end-users is negatively affecting the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of patient data [17]. If not addressed there might be escalation of the problem and its adverse effects as well. Previous studies have focused on cybersecurity policy and legislation mainly for cyber defenders, cyber service providers, and institutional-level strategies. Given the scope of the emerging problem being much linked to end-users then, this study aimed to link patient data protection with cybersecurity practices by system end-users.

Objective of the Study

The objective of this study is to examine the shortcomings of current cyber security practices by healthcare system end-users in patients' data protection. What cybersecurity measures are currently in place at Peramiho Mission Hospital? To what extent are the end-system users knowledgeable on data protection protocols? What are the most common cybersecurity threats at Peramiho Mission Hospital? How can end-users improve skills on ensuring patient data security?

LITERATURE REVIEW

[18] studied the state of research on cyberattacks against hospitals and available best practice recommendations. The study employed mixed methods as commonly applicable in meta-analysis of previous studies. The study used data from four databases including PubMed, Web of Science, ProQuest, and Scopus. The study found that context (such as the case of system end - users' aspect) and trends in cybersecurity was only covered by 27.8% of research in a period of 20 years from 1997 to 2017. Also, the study found that there was no sufficient research on comprehensive guidelines and standardized best practice measures. The study signifies paucity of information regarding system end-user best practices which is yet the center of cybersecurity mainly related to internal attacks.

Moreover, [19] conducted a study on patient's data privacy protection in medical healthcare transmission services using back propagation learning. The study aimed to address the privacy issues among the end-user and the healthcare center with a focus on enhancing data integrity through the use of encryption and decryption. The study emphasizes on three options to safeguard data protection in healthcare systems ranging from authentication, consistency, and accessibility. The study focused on these three cornerstones of cybersecurity in the light of the system but little is said regarding end-user's practices related to authentication, consistency, and accessibility.

Furthermore, a study by [20] investigated risk management focusing on identifying requirements and best practices for healthcare data security systems. The study was qualitative and used secondary data mainly from studies on state-of-the-art data security systems. Content analysis of assertive keywords, source-selection criteria, interpretation of selected articles, and database analysis of previous research articles. The study found that information generated through healthcare systems was rich in content making cybersecurity crucial for the healthcare sector. It was also evident that cybersecurity was neglected by health institutions were not effectively dealing with the reality of cyberthreats. The study highlights on the need to prioritize cybersecurity as the institution level. The area of end-users taking into account patient data protection as core aspect of cybersecurity is not given attention.

Nevertheless, a study by [21] aimed to address unknown aspects of information security awareness scale (ISA) in its conceptualization, data collection and analysis during ISA development and scale validation. The study employed Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) method. With the PRISMA method both qualitative assessment of the methodology used in previous studies, and the quantitative estimation of the number of studies included in the meta-analysis. The study relied on secondary data mainly from 24 research articles. Descriptive and content analysis methods were used to arrive at conclusions. The study found that human factors such as their practices play an important role in information security of any organization. It is best practice for system users not only to comprehend the significance of information security issues and threats but also to follow the organizations' privacy and security rules. The study highlights best practices of considering client information as important and compliance with privacy and security rules. However, practices to ensure relevance of organizations' privacy and security rules to actual needs and internal control practices to guarantee their enforcement not addressed.

The study was guided by the Identity theory. The Identity theory was propounded by Sheldon Stryker in 1968 which establishes that there are identities attached to a particular role [22]. Proponents of the theory argue that its relevance with security compliance behaviors highlights a nexus between

different factors and motivations for security [23]. The theoretical concept of identity is burgeoning in information systems (IS) which the healthcare management information systems are part of [24].

In the context of this study, the theory can be applied to probe system end-users' identity of their role in ensuring patient data protection. The theory demands that system end-users have to have conceived in their attitude what ought to be their role as related to patient data protection [1]. Such a cognition and role of patient data protection can be realized partly through system end-users understanding and application of cybersecurity best practices [25]. Thus, the theory suggests that prevailing data breaches in healthcare facilities can be associated with a lack of technical know-how and inability to apply cybersecurity best practices among system end-users as they lack self-identity as cybersecurity agents [26]. Thus, the aforementioned axiom of this theory will be used to explain confidentiality of patient data, integrity of patient data as well as availability of patient data through system end-users' cognition and application of cybersecurity best practices in healthcare facilities.

METHODOLOGY

The study applied mixed methods to accommodate both quantitative and qualitative methods. Thus, a cross-sectional design used to facilitate access to data cutting across different tasks of system end-users. The study was conducted at Peramiho Hospital located in Ruvuma the southern region of Tanzania. The area was suitable as there were incidences related to data breach associated with system end-users. The population of the study included 268 system end-users from 11 departments at the study area. The sample included 170 system end-users based on the Solven's formula of sample estimation at the 5% confidence level. The response rate at the end of the study was 161 out of 170 system end-users indicating 94.7% response rate. Thus, primary data were collected using self-administered questionnaires from 161 system end-users who were randomly selected from different departments at the facility. Moreover, 10 heads of departments and 1 senior ICT officer were interviewed as they were key custodians of key information for their respective departments given their level of seniority. On the other hand, secondary data were collected using documentary guide. Secondary data included data on incidences of data breach and policy guidelines of the organization regarding patient data protection. Quantitative data were analysed using the SPSS package version 26 especially for data entry, and data analysis for generating descriptive statistics. Additionally, R package version 4.3.4 was used to graphically visualize data and produce correlation analysis results. On the other hand, qualitative data were analysed using the thematic analysis methods referring to the six stages given by [27]. The stages are described here as follows: familiarize with data, data coding, search for topics (themes and sub-themes); evaluate the themes; define and name the themes; and finally, the report writing.

RESULTS AND FINDINGS

The purpose of the study was to examine the shortcomings of cybersecurity practices by healthcare system end-users in patient's data protection. The findings are organized with regard to the description of the problem of patient data breach at the study area, the level of data protection, the shortcomings of the cybersecurity practices by healthcare system end-users regarding patient's data protection.

Demographic Findings

The demographic findings include the sex of respondents, age, education level and working experience at Peramiho Hospital. The results are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Demographics of Respondents

Parameter	Category	Frequency	Percent
Sex	Male	70	43.5
	Female	91	56.5
	Total	161	100
Education	Certificate	35	21.7

	Diploma	58	36
	Higher education	68	42.2
	Total	161	100
Age	18-35	37	23
	36-55	71	44.1
	56 and above	53	32.9
	Total	161	100
Working experience	2-3 years	26	16.1
	4-5 years	57	35.4
	6+ years	78	48.4
	Total	161	100

The results in Table 1 show that out of 161 respondents, 43.5% were Male and 56.5% were Female. Majority were female who in most cases are associated with cybersecurity vulnerabilities compared to their counterpart males (UN Women and UN University Institute in Macau, 2024). Also, the results show that out of 161 respondents, 21.7% had Certificate education, 36% had Diploma education, and 42.2% had Higher education. Respondents were literate indicating that the use of self-administered questionnaires during data collection was relevant. Also, the results show that out of 161 respondents, 23% were between 18-35 years old, 44.1% were between 36-55 years old, 32.9% were 56+ years old. Majority of respondents were beyond the youth age cut off (35 years) indicating extra efforts of training for system use in relation to security and data protection would require extra efforts which is inconsistent with a study by (Omar et al., 2021). Nevertheless, the results show that out of 161 respondents, 16.1% had 2-3 years of working experience, 35.4% had 4-5 years of working experience and 48.4 had 6+ years of working experience. Respondents had a good experience at the work place insinuating reliability of results based on respondent having relevant exposure to the study context as system end users at the study area.

Description of the Problem of Patient Data Breach at the Study Area

This was a preliminary analysis of the problem in order to ascertain the scope of failures in patient data protection at the study area. Secondary data were used including the recorded incidences of data breach by end-users. Also, the interviews were conducted to shed light on the incidences and how they could have affected data protection. The results are presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Incidences of Patient Data Breach at the Study Area

The results in Figure 1 show that there was increasing trend of data breach incidences initiated or facilitated by system end-users at PMH. The data breach incidences had increased from 1 incidence in 2022 to 6 incidences in 2023, before the number doubled to 12 incidences in about eight months of the year 2024. The findings suggest there was little that was being done to prevent reoccurrence of the incidences. However, the finding implies there was limited consideration of cybersecurity best

practices of system end-users at the study area. On the other hand, based on thematic analysis results the reported incidences of data breach had affected the level of data protection in terms of lack of confidentiality, lack of integrity and availability of patient data. This finding aligns with the key informant who had the following views: -

“The incidences related to patient data may range from unintended use, disclosure of data without consent and forgery of data which affects the integrity, confidentiality and the availability of patient data” (K11, 18 August 2024)

The finding aligns with the reported incidences which constitute increasing trend from 1 incidence in the year 2022 to 5 incidences in the year 2024 for unintended use, and from 2 incidences in the year 2023 to 4 incidences in the year 2024 for documentation forgery, and from 1 incidence in the year 2023 to 3 incidences in the year 2024 for unauthorized disclosure of patient data. Thus, data protection is consistently at stake in form of unintended use, documentation forgery, and unauthorized disclosure of patient data negatively affecting integrity, confidentiality and availability of patient data. This was further affirmed through the moderate level of data protection reflecting uncertainty on the five-point likert scale as shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Means Score on Patient Data Protection

Cybersecurity practice	Mean	St. Dev	Level	Reflecting
Integrity of patient data	3.18	0.83	Moderate	Uncertain
Confidentiality of patient data	2.67	0.65	Moderate	Uncertain
Availability of patient data	4.24	0.14	Very high	Strongly agree
Overall	3.36	0.80	Moderate	Uncertain

Based on the findings, it is imperative to examine the shortcomings of current cybersecurity practices by healthcare system end-users in patient’s data protection.

The Shortcomings of Cybersecurity Practices in Relation to Patient Data Protection

This was the main focus of the study that intended to examine the shortcomings of cybersecurity practices by healthcare system end-users in patient’s data protection. The results are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. The Level of Cybersecurity Practices

Cybersecurity practice	Mean	St. Dev	Level
End-user conception of significance of data protection	3.07	0.91	Moderate
End-users getting trained on data protection	2.39	0.96	Low
Compliance monitoring and auditing	1.84	0.84	Low
Overall	2.43	0.62	Low

Limited End-User Conception of the Significance of Data Protection

The results in Table 2 show that the mean score of end-user conception of significance of data protection was 3.07 which indicates moderate level according to five-point likert scale. The finding indicates system end-users were not fully into taking data protection as of significance and part of their role as it ought to be. This was a misalignment with the identity theory which requires that system end-users need to perceive themselves as agents of data protection and have a positive attitude towards cybersecurity best practices. The finding aligns with the thematic analysis results which show that majority of system end-users were lacking cognition of their pivotal role as key players in data protection. For example, the key informant had the following to say: -

“Of course, it is expected that all system users should play certain roles to protect data but most of them don’t take it seriously because they think it’s the sole duty of the ICT officer” (K12, 18 August 2024)

As noted from the findings above, it is reasonable to conclude that best practices of system end-users were not common partly due to lack of self-involvement of end-users in data protection. Based on this phenomenon it was not surprising to find that the mishandling of login details was common as shown in the figure 2 below.

Figure 2. End-User Malpractices Related to System Login Details

Correlation between the Conception of Significance of Data Protection and Data Protection

In this part, the researchers aimed to link independent variable namely end-user conception of the significance of data protection, and the dependent variable namely data protection using the statistical methods of correlation analysis. The measurements of variables were following the ordinal ranking of five-point likert scale. Thus, the Spearman's rank correlation method was appropriate. The researcher chose to use the 95% confidence interval. The results are presented in Figure 3. The results in Figure 3 show that there is a very strong positive correlation between independent variable namely end-user conception of the significance of data protection and the dependent variable namely data protection at 1% level of significance [$r_s = 0.85$, $p\text{-value} < 0.001$]. The finding justifies a significant monotonous relationship between end-user training on data protection and data protection.

Figure 3. Spearman's Rank Correlation Results

Inadequacy of End-Users Training on Data Protection

The results in Table 2 show that the mean score of end-user training on data protection was 2.39 which indicates low level according to five-point likert scale. The finding indicates there was

inadequate training of system end-users regarding patient data protection. The finding aligns with the thematic analysis results which show that training was not regular and mainly involved new system users, focused on the technical issues to enhance user ability in application of the system. The finding was in agreement with the key informants who had the following to say: -

“Training on system usage is part of the induction training for new entrants, unlike recently, we did not experience problems related to data theft years back and could not emphasize on data protection” (KI3, 17 August 2024)

The findings indicate the scope of training was limited to special occasions with a focus on system application and very limited emphasis on data protection.

Correlation between End-Users Training and Data Protection

In this part, the researchers aimed to link end-user training on data protection and data protection using the statistical methods of correlation analysis. The measurements of variables were following the ordinal ranking of five-point likert scale. Thus, the Spearman’s rank correlation method was appropriate. The researcher chose to use the 95% confidence interval. The results are presented in Figure 4. The results in Figure 4 show that there is a very strong positive correlation between end-user training on data protection and data protection at 1% level of significance [$r_s = 0.90$, $p\text{-value} < 0.001$]. The finding justifies a significant monotonous relationship between end-user training on data protection and data protection.

Figure 4. Spearman’s Rank Correlation Results

Lack of End-User Compliance Monitoring

The results in Table 2 show that the mean score of end-user compliance monitoring and auditing was 1.84 which indicates very low level according to five-point likert scale. The finding indicates that end-user compliance monitoring and auditing was very uncommon which would negatively affect patient data protection. In line with this finding, the thematic analysis results show that end - user compliance monitoring was triggered by the happening of cyber incidences of data breach and was not system based, neither special internal end-user compliance audits nor external end - user compliance auditing was ever conducted. The finding was further supported by the key informant who had the following to say: -

“We do monitor through incidence reporting but we do not have sophisticated and systematic monitoring of end-user behaviors on regular basis” (KI4, 20 August 2024)

Another key informant had the following views: -

“We have never conducted audits to see extent to which end-users comply with best practices” (KI3, 17 August 2024)

The findings indicate that there was ineffective monitoring of the end - user compliance with best practices that would guarantee patient data protection.

Correlation between End-User Compliance Monitoring and Data Protection

In this part the researcher aimed to link end-user compliance monitoring with the data protection using the statistical methods of correlation analysis. The measurements of variables were following the ordinal ranking of five-point likert scale. Thus, the Spearman's rank correlation method was appropriate. The researcher chose to use the 95% confidence interval. The results are presented in Figure 5. The results in Figure 3 show that there is a very strong positive correlation between end-user compliance monitoring and data protection at 1% level of significance [$r_s = 0.89$, $p\text{-value} < 0.001$]. The finding justifies a significant monotonous relationship between end-user compliance monitoring and data protection.

Figure 5. Spearman's Rank Correlation Results

DISCUSSIONS

The objective of this study was to examine the shortcomings of cybersecurity practices by healthcare system end-users in patient's data protection. The results show that there was increasing trend of data breach incidences initiated or facilitated by system end-users at PMH. The finding implies there was limited consideration of cybersecurity best practices of system end-users at the study area. On the other hand, the reported incidences of data breach had affected the level of data protection in terms of lack of confidentiality, lack of integrity and availability of patient data. Thus, patient data protection was consistently at stake in form of unintended use, documentation forgery, and unauthorized disclosure of patient data which in turn compromised the level of data protection to the moderate level reflecting uncertainty on the five-point likert scale. Based on the findings, it is imperative to examine the shortcomings of current cybersecurity practices by healthcare system end-users in patient's data protection. The study found that the shortcomings of cybersecurity practices in relation to patient data protection include limited end-user conception of the significance of data protection, inadequacy of end-users training on data protection, and the lack of end-user compliance monitoring.

In respect of end-user conception of the significance of data protection, the study found that there was a very strong positive significant relationship between end-user conception of the significance of data protection and the level of data protection [$r_s = 0.85$, $p\text{-value} < 0.001$]. However, system end-users were not fully into taking data protection as of significance and part of their role as it ought to be. This was a misalignment with the identity theory which requires that system end-users need to perceive themselves as agents of data protection and have a positive attitude towards cybersecurity best practices [26]. The study concludes that best practices of system end-users were not common partly due to lack of self-involvement of end-users in data protection. End-users were much more

concerned with using the system for prescribed duties but not so much concerned with ensuring confidentiality of data, integrity of data or availability of data. This finding suggests that patient data protection was not highly considered as a function of practices by system end-users thus misaligning with suggestion from the previous study finding that human factors such as their practices play an important role in information security of any organization [21].

Regarding training of system end-users on data protection, there was a very strong positive significant relationship between end-user training on data protection and data protection [$r_s = 0.90$, $p\text{-value} < 0.001$]. The finding justifies a significant monotonous relationship between end-user training on data protection and data protection. However, there was inadequacy of end-users training on data protection in turn compromising patient data protection [28]. The finding implies that end-users were not equipped with cyberthreat awareness and related skills to protect patient data from unauthorized access.

The lack of cyberthreat awareness and related skills to protect patient data among end-users is associated with increasing trend of data breaches. The finding aligns with the provisions of the Identity Theory which suggests that prevailing data breaches in healthcare facilities would result from the lack of technical know-how and inability to apply cybersecurity best practices among system end-users as they lack self-identity as cybersecurity agents [26]. This link is further complimented by proponents of the identity theory who argues that system end-users understanding and application of cybersecurity best practices facilitate their cognition as cybersecurity agents with the role of patient data protection [25].

Regarding end-user compliance monitoring, there was a very strong positive significant relationship between end-user compliance monitoring and data protection [$r_s = 0.89$, $p\text{-value} < 0.001$]. Thus, when system end-users are subjected to higher levels of regular monitoring of their compliance with cybersecurity practices, they would exhibit relatively higher levels of ensuring patient data protection and vice versa is also true, holding other things the same. However, the study found that end-user compliance monitoring and auditing was very uncommon which negatively affected patient data protection. Based on the findings there was ineffective monitoring of the end-user compliance with best practices that would guarantee patient data protection. The ineffective monitoring was characterized by lack of regular monitoring schedule, lack of terms of reference for monitoring and lack of end-user compliance audit culture which are vital aspects of security compliance monitoring [29]. This problem is linked to the problem of data breach since the end-users are not subjected to intense perceived risk of data breach. It means end-users are not subjected to possibility of being easily noticed, and being reported as they play negligent or collaborate for patient data breach. The finding implies that there was underutilization of end-users as agents of data protection as suggested by the identity theory guiding this study [26]. In line with the identity theory end-users need to be acknowledged as agents of data protection to be able to ensure insider activities are put to light through effective monitoring mechanisms [30].

Conclusion

The study concludes that data protection in healthcare sector is a function of cybersecurity best practices of system end-users among other things. This is informed by the very strong positive relationship between cybersecurity best practices including the system end-user conception of the significance of data protection [$r_s = 0.85$, $p\text{-value} < 0.001$], the system end-user training on data protection [$r_s = 0.90$, $p\text{-value} < 0.001$], and the system end-user compliance monitoring [$r_s = 0.89$, $p\text{-value} < 0.001$]. Thus, the moderate level of data protection was a result of the shortcomings in cybersecurity best practices. The study found there was limited end-user conception of the significance of data protection, inadequacy of end-users training on data protection, and the lack of end-user compliance monitoring. These shortcomings were associated with the compromised data protection in terms of unguaranteed integrity, lack of confidentiality and availability of patient data. This was also reflected in the increasing trend of incidences involving unintended use of patient data, documentation forgery of patient data, and unauthorized disclosure of patient data.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Institutional organizations of healthcare sectors may need to streamline cybersecurity best practices for system end-users to ensure patient data protection. This can be achieved through regular training, security hardening and mechanism for regular monitoring of end-user compliance to best practices. Future studies may need to focus on effective ways to improve cybersecurity best practices of system end-users.

REFERENCES

- [1] S.K Beura, R. Dhapola, A .R Panigrahi, P. Yadav, R. Kumar, D. H. Reddy and S.K Singh "Antiplatelet drugs: potential therapeutic options for the management of neurodegenerative diseases". *Medicinal Research Reviews*, 43(6), pp.1835-1877, 2023.
- [2] A. H. Seh, M. Zarour, M. Alenezi, A. K. Sarkar, A. Agrawal, R. Kumar, and R. A. Khan, "Healthcare data breaches: Insights and implications," *Healthcare (Basel)*, vol. 8, no. 2, Art. 133, May 13, 2020. doi: 10.3390/healthcare8020133.
- [3] S. M. Musa, U. A. Haruna, E. Manirambona, G. Eshun, D. M. Ahmad, D. A. Dada, A. A. Gololo, S. S. Musa, A. K. Abdulkadir, and D. E. Lucero-Priso III, "Paucity of health data in Africa: An obstacle to digital health implementation and evidence-based practice," *Public Health Rev.*, vol. 44, Art. 1605821, Aug. 29, 2023, doi: 10.3389/phrs.2023.1605821.
- [4] N. S Dean, "Healthcare Data Breaches: Analysis and Prevention" 2023.
- [5] N. Jerry-Egemma, "Safe and sound: strengthening cybersecurity in healthcare through robust staff educational programs. In *Healthcare Management Forum@* (Vol. 37, No. 1, pp. 21-25). Sage CA: Los Angeles, CA: SAGE Publications, January 2024
- [6] M.U. Tariq, "Enhancing cybersecurity protocols in modern healthcare systems: Strategies and best practices. In *Transformative approaches to patient literacy and healthcare innovation*" (pp. 223-241). IGI Global. 2024
- [7] E. Busingye, "Adoption and use of cybersecurity in the financial sector in developing countries" (Doctoral dissertation, Uganda Martyrs University). 2016
- [8] B. A. Townsend, "Privacy and data protection in eHealth in Africa-an assessment of the regulatory frameworks that govern privacy and data protection in the effective implementation of electronic health care in Africa: is there a need for reform and greater regional collaboration in regulatory policymaking?" 2017
- [9] A. Folorunso, "Information Security Management Systems (ISMS) on patient information protection within the healthcare industry in Oyo, Nigeria". Nigeria (April 12, 2024).
- [10] C. Cross, "Dissent as cybercrime: social media, security and development in Tanzania," *J. East Afr. Stud.*, vol. 15, no. 3, pp. 442–463, 2021.
- [11] E. Kayumbe and E. Gilliard, "Cybersecurity in Tanzania: Opportunities and challenges," *Int. J. Finance & Manage. Res.*, vol. 6, 2024, Art. 14058, doi: 10.36948/ijfmr.2024.v06i01.14058.
- [12] C. Mambile and P. Mbogoro, "Cybercrimes awareness, cyber laws and its practice in public sector of Tanzania," *Int. J. Adv. Technol. Eng. Explor.*, vol. 7, no. 68, 2020, Art. 119.
- [13] M. Selemani, V. Ndume, and D. Kisanga, "Integrating ICT in Tanzania secondary schools: experience of Tanzania as it grows to second world economy," *Int. J. Educ.*, vol. 2, pp. 81–95, 2021.
- [14] M. Al Kinoon, "A Comprehensive and Comparative Examination of Healthcare Data Breaches: Assessing Security, Privacy, and Performance".2024
- [15] T.T Smith, "Examining data privacy breaches in healthcare". Walden University, 2026
- [16] D. S. Tesha, "Assessing Factors Affecting Data Privacy in Local Government Authorities in Tanzania" (Doctoral dissertation, Institute of Accountancy Arusha (IAA)), 2022

- [17] M. L. Rustad and T. H. Koenig, "Towards a global data privacy standard", *Fla. L. Rev.*, 71, p.365, 2019.
- [18] S. T. Argaw, N. E. Bempong, B. Eshaya-Chauvin, et al., "The state of research on cyberattacks against hospitals and available best practice recommendations: a scoping review," *BMC Med. Inform. Decis. Mak.*, vol. 19, Art. 10, 2019, doi: 10.1186/s12911-018-0724-5.
- [19] A. Altameem, V. Kovtun, M. Al-Ma'aitah, T. Altameem and A. E. Youssef. "Patient's data privacy protection in medical healthcare transmission services using back propagation learning". *Computers and Electrical Engineering*, 102, p.108087, 2022
- [20] F. M. Dias, M. L. Martens, S. F. de P. Monken, L. F. Silva, and E. D. R. Santibanez-Gonzalez, "Risk management focusing on the best practices of data security systems for healthcare," *Int. J. Innovation (IJ)*, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 45–78, Jan.–Apr. 2021, doi: 10.5585/iji.v9i1.18246.
- [21] R. Rohani, D. P. Debajyoti, H. Jari, S. F. Suree, C. Wichian, and H. Thimphu, "A systematic literature review of cybersecurity scales assessing information security awareness," *Heliyon*, vol. 9, no. 3, e14234, 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e14234.
- [22] S. Stryker and P. J. Burke, "The past, present, and future of an identity theory. *Social psychology quarterly*", pp.284-297, 2000
- [23] H. Pham, L. Brennan and J. Richardson, "Review of behavioural theories in security compliance and research challenge". In *Informing Science and Information Technology Education Conference, Vietnam (Vol. 31, pp. 65-76)*, June 2017. Santa Rosa, CA: Informing Science Institute.
- [24] Desrochers, P.R., 2024. Access to Information and Privacy: Practical Approaches for Public Service Reform. *Canadian Public Administration*, 67(4), pp.562-572.
- [25] P. Kautwima, T. Haiduwa, K. Sai, V. Hashiyana, and N. Suresh, "System end-user actions as a threat to information system security," *Int. J. Network Security Its Appl.*, vol. 13, pp. 71–83, 2021, doi: 10.5121/ijnsa.2021.13606.
- [26] A. H. Almulihi, F. Alassery, A. I. Khan, S. Shukla, B. K. Gupta and R. Kumar, "Analyzing the Implications of Healthcare Data Breaches through Computational Technique". *Intelligent Automation & Soft Computing*, 32(3), 2022.
- [27] V. Braun, V. Clarke and D. Gray. "Innovations in qualitative methods. *The Palgrave handbook of critical social psychology*", pp.243-266, 2017
- [28] E. Dymoke, "Why you need end user security training (making the business case)," *Hoxhunt*, Apr. 12, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://hoxhunt.com/blog/end-user-security-training>
- [29] J. Vigo, "Security compliance monitoring: best practices," *Jamf*, Feb. 15, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.jamf.com/blog/security-compliance-monitoring-best-practices/>
- [30] D. Kashyap, "How do you involve end-users in your cybersecurity solutions?," *LinkedIn*, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.linkedin.com/advice/0/how-do-you-involve-end-users-your-cybersecurity-solutions>

